

Cardiovascular disease in the literature: A selection of recent original research papers

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3 **Potential Effects of Coronaviruses on the Cardiovascular System: A Review.** *JAMA Cardiol.*
4 doi:10.1001/jamacardio.2020.1286.
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8 Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome
9 coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), has been declared a pandemic with devastating effects on the
10 entire world. Madjid et al. from the University of Texas Health Science, Houston, Texas review
11 current information on the virus and COVID-19 and its effects on the cardiovascular system.
12 Coronaviruses, classified in 4 groups, were first identified in humans in the 1960s with 4 types
13 (all from the α and β classes) are endemic in humans usually causing mild and self-limiting
14 upper respiratory infections accounting for 15-30% of common colds. Both SARS (caused by
15 SARS-CoV) and Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS, caused by MERS-CoV) caused
16 outbreaks (in 2002 and 2012, respectively) that had higher fatality rates but were much less
17 widespread than COVID-19. SARS-CoV-2 is genetically more similar to SARS-CoV (82%) than
18 MERS-CoV (50%). The virus has a mean incubation period of 5.2 days (95%CI, 4.1-7.0 days),
19 with the 95th percentile of the distribution at 12.5 days according to one study and up to 14 days
20 according to another. The World Health Organization reported a global mortality rate of 3.4%
21 but importantly, this rate varies by location, intensity of transmission, variations of care,
22 presence of comorbidities (including cardiovascular disease), advanced age, and likely other
23 factors. The primary symptoms of COVID-19 are fever, cough, and shortness of breath. Acute
24 cardiac injury determined by elevated high-sensitivity troponin levels is commonly observed in
25 severe cases and is strongly associated with mortality, complications such as acute respiratory
26 distress syndrome, arrhythmia, renal injury, and coagulopathy. There has been reported cases of
27 viral infiltration of the myocardium causing myocarditis. Myocardial injury can also be caused
28 by ischemia. It is important to note that COVID-19 in addition to inducing new cardiac
29 pathologies (such as myocarditis) may also exacerbate pre-existing cardiovascular disease.
30 Finally, some of the investigational therapies for COVID-19 may have cardiovascular effects.
31 Current treatment, until investigational therapies have been shown to be effective, is supportive
32 care and treatment of complications. The article offers a wonderful review of current knowledge
33 on COVID-19 as well as a review of SARS and MERS which provide further insights on the
34 effects of coronaviruses on the cardiovascular system.
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3 **Association of Public Health Interventions With the Epidemiology of the COVID-19 Outbreak in**
4 **Wuhan, China.** JAMA 2020. doi:10.1001/jama.2020.6130.
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6 **Background:** Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) has become a pandemic. Pan An et al. from Tongji
7 Medical College, Wuhan, China, sought to assess whether different public health interventions during 5
8 consecutive periods could improve control of the outbreak in Wuhan: Period 1 (Dec 8-Jan 9)-No
9 intervention; Period 2 (Jan 10-22)-Massive human movement due to Chinese New Year; Period 3 (Jan
10 11-Feb 1)-implementation of home quarantine, traffic restriction, cordon sanitaire; Period 4 (Feb 2-16)-
11 Centralized quarantine; Period 5 (Feb 17-march 8)-Universal symptoms survey. Individual-level data on
12 laboratory-confirmed COVID-19 cases were extracted from the municipal Notifiable Disease Report
13 System. The rates of laboratory-confirmed COVID-19 infections and the effective reproduction number
14 of SARS-CoV-2 (an indicator of secondary transmission) were calculated and compared for each of the 5
15 periods.
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19 **Findings:** Among 32 583 laboratory-confirmed COVID-19 cases (median age 57 years, 52% women), the
20 daily confirmed case rate peaked in the third period and declined afterward across geographic regions,
21 gender and age groups. Local health care workers were significantly more affected than the general
22 population (130.5 per million people vs. 41.5 per million people) in the early periods, an indicator of
23 nosocomial infection due to lower awareness and inadequate use of personal protective equipment in
24 the early periods, and quickly decreased in the subsequent periods. Severe and critical cases decreased
25 from 53.1% to 10.3% over the 5 periods.
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28 **Significance:** The institution of interventions including cordons sanitaire, traffic restriction, social
29 distancing, home quarantine, centralized quarantine, and universal symptom survey was temporally
30 associated with reduction of new confirmed cases and secondary transmission of COVID-19 across age
31 groups, sex, and geographic regions. These findings may be valuable in the current efforts to combat the
32 global pandemic of COVID-19 as they underscore the importance of public awareness and early
33 implementation of multifaceted public health interventions. The limited testing in the first periods as
34 well as under-reporting of asymptomatic cases probably underestimated the numbers. Also, because of
35 the implementation of multiple public interventions at the same time, the impact of each individual
36 strategy cannot be inferred.
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3 **Cardiac troponin I in patients with coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19): Evidence from a meta-**
4 **analysis.** Progress in Cardiovascular Diseases, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pcad.2020.03.001>.
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8 **Background:** Patients with cardiovascular disease are at higher risk for complications and death with
9 COVID-19. Lippi et al. from University of Verona, Italy performed a meta-analysis of studies that
10 investigated the association between cardiac troponin and severity of COVID-19.
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12 **Results:** After excluding non-pertinent paper, 4 studies were included. All 4 studies used cardiac
13 troponin I, and all except one used high-sensitivity assays. All 4 studies were from China and included a
14 total of 341 patients (36% with severe disease). The clinical outcome was defined as intensive care unit
15 admission in 2 studies, acute respiratory distress syndrome in one study, and death in one study. Cardiac
16 troponin I was significantly higher in patients with severe COVID-19 compared to those without severe
17 disease (standardized mean difference 25.6 ng/L; 95% CI, 6.8–44.5 ng/L). There was significant
18 heterogeneity between studies (I^2 , 98%; $p < 0.001$).
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21 **Significance:** Elevated cardiac troponin in patients with COVID-19 indicates the presence of cardiac
22 injury which is associated with more severe disease, higher rate of complications, and higher likelihood
23 of death. Whether stratifying treatment strategies by troponin elevation will be useful in management
24 of these patients remains to be seen.
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3 **Epidemiology of Covid-19 in a Long-Term Care Facility in King County, Washington.** N Eng J Med 2020.
4 DOI: 10.1056/NEJMoa2005412.
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8 **Background:** The vulnerability of long-term care facilities residents to respiratory disease outbreaks is
9 well known. Due to their advanced age and underlying chronic health conditions, they are at increased
10 risk for severe complications and poor outcomes from outbreaks of COVID-19. After the identification
11 on February 28, 2020 of a confirmed case of COVID-19 in a skilled nursing facility in King County,
12 Washington, McMicheal T et al. from the Public Health–Seattle and King County aided by the Centers for
13 Disease Control and Prevention, launched an investigation with contact tracing, quarantined exposed
14 persons, isolated confirmed and suspected cases in an effort to contain the disease.
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17 **Findings:** As of March 18 2020, less than 3 weeks from the first identified case, a total of 167 confirmed
18 cases of COVID-19 (median age 72 years, 67% female) were found to be epidemiologically linked to the
19 facility; they included 101 residents, 50 health care personnel, and 16 visitors. The majority of cases
20 among residents had respiratory symptoms, and only 7% were asymptomatic. The hospitalization rates
21 for facility residents, visitors, and staff were 55%, 50%, and 6%, with corresponding case fatality rates of
22 34%, 0%, and 6%. In addition, a total of 30 long-term care facilities with at least one confirmed case of
23 Covid-19 had been identified in King County were identified within this short period.
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26 **Significance:** The study underscores the high transmission rate of COVID-19, and the vulnerability of
27 long-term care facility residents with one-third case fatality rate. Staff working in multiple facilities while
28 ill and the transfer of patients from one facility to another are potential causes of spread. Proactive
29 steps to identify and exclude potentially infected staff and visitors, and implementation of appropriate
30 infection prevention and control measures, are necessary to halt the spread of the disease. On March
31 10, the governor of Washington implemented mandatory screening of health care workers and visitor
32 restrictions for all licensed nursing homes and assisted living facilities.
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3 **Compassionate Use of Remdesivir for Patients with Severe Covid-19.** N Engl J Med 2020. DOI:
4 10.1056/NEJMoa2007016.
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8 **Background:** Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) has become a pandemic with alarming transmission and
9 death rates. Grein J et al. from Cedars–Sinai Medical Center, Los Angeles, investigated the
10 compassionate use of Remdesivir, a nucleotide analogue prodrug that inhibits viral RNA polymerases
11 with in vitro activity against SARS-CoV-2, in 61 patients hospitalized with COVID-19. Inclusion criteria
12 included patients with confirmed SARS-CoV-2 infection, oxygen saturation less or equal to 94% on room
13 air or the requirement of oxygen support. Patients received a 10-day course of Remdesivir, consisting of
14 200 mg administered intravenously on day 1, followed by 100 mg daily for the remaining 9 days of
15 treatment.
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18 **Findings:** Between January 25 to March 7 2020, 53 patients (22 in the United States, 22 in Europe or
19 Canada, and 9 in Japan) received compassionate use of Remdesivir and had available post-treatment
20 data for analysis. Almost 65% of the patients were on high oxygen support measures at baseline (57%
21 ventilators, 8% extracorporeal membrane oxygenation). After a median follow-up of 18 days, two-third
22 had an improvement in oxygen-support class, with more than half of those on ventilators getting
23 extubated. A total of 25 patients (47%) were discharged. The overall mortality rate was 13% (7/53) and
24 was significantly higher for those receiving invasive ventilation (6/34, 18%) compared to those not on
25 ventilator (1/19, 5%).
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29 **Significance:** In this cohort of sick patients hospitalized for severe COVID-19 and requiring oxygen
30 support, the compassionate-use of Remdesivir resulted in clinical improvement of two-third of patients.
31 The exclusion of 8/61 patients due to unavailable data post-treatment, and the lack of a control group
32 are significant limitations of this study. Randomized, placebo controlled trials are needed to validate the
33 results of this small size uncontrolled study, and those trials are ongoing. The challenge of conducting
34 fast randomized clinical trials trying to fight a pandemic is a global challenge and requires putting
35 everyone's resources and expertise.
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